

STRUCTURAL RESPONSE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES TO BLAST LOAD

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SUMMARY

The paper deals with 3D Finite Element (FEM) simulations of fully clamped rectangular Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) composite plates subjected to blast loads generated by C4 explosive charges. The work compares experimental data with numerical results carried out using LS-DYNA commercial code.

Keywords: Blast, impact, CFRP, FEM, LS-DYNA

ABSTRACT

As a consequence of different accidental or intentional events, such as terroristic attacks and guerrilla warfare, the behaviour of structural materials under blast load has received considerable attention in recent years. Due to their high specific properties, fibre-reinforced polymers are being considered for use in a wide range of structural applications where their low weight and resistance to blast loading are of importance, such as Armoured Fighting Vehicle (AFV) hulls. A deep insight into the relationship between explosion loads, composite architecture and deformation / fracture behaviour will offer the possibility to design lightweight structures with significantly enhanced energy absorption and blast resistance.

This work deals with 3D numerical simulations of damage caused by air blast on fully clamped composite rectangular plates. This study examines the performance of CFRP laminates subjected to blast loads using commercial LS-DYNA software, including a cohesive damage model to represent delamination. The blast load was simulated using a Multi Materials Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian (MMALE) approach, with Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) between the Eulerian blast and Lagrangian target models.

The simulation results are presented and compared with the experimental data, showing good agreement in terms of damage distribution and damage assessment.

Introduction

Modern military vehicles are a compromise between the need of a great mobility and the increasing payload request [1]. These fairly opposite design requirements are leading the

development of lightweight AFVs and research into lightweight vehicle structures are playing an important role in this process. With the associated request for lighter protection systems, there has been an increasing move towards armour systems which are both structural and protection components at the same time. Fibre-reinforced composite materials respond to this demand as an acceptable combination of structural performance and low density. In particular, CFRP composites exhibit excellent specific structural properties and since the costs of experimental trials are usually very high, numerical FEM analysis can be a useful tool in order to minimize the number of experiments and also to understand general phenomenological aspects.

Pioneering works regarding the response of structural components to blast loads were focused on homogenous metal beams and plates [2-11]. These studies investigated the effect of boundary, load and material properties on the failure morphologies.

The first studies regarding the effects of blast loads on composite structures concerned the effects of underwater blast shock on fibre-reinforced polymer matrix composites. Mouritz and co-workers investigated the effect on the fatigue life, damage, failure and bending properties [12-14]. They showed that glass reinforced plastic (GRP) panels backed by air and loaded by underwater blast wave at low overpressure exhibit only matrix cracking, while, as load increases, the damage appears in form of fibre failure and delamination. Regarding analytical and numerical works, although modelling of blast impact on structures is quite complex due to the dependence on both load history and boundary conditions, a rather wide literature about prediction of structures behavior under blast load can be found. In the 90s Olson and Nurick analysed stiffened and un-stiffened clamped square mild steel plates under uniformly distributed blast load [9, 15]. In the case of un-stiffened plate the non linear numerical models showed mode I, mode II and a trend towards mode III failure as the load intensity increases. In 2001 Wang [16] presented a benchmark work of simulation of explosion in soil and air using LS-DYNA commercial code and Eulerian formulation. From this report it appears that for a landmine explosion simulation results are in a satisfactory agreement with experiments. Although the predicted pressure is in certain cases 50% greater than the measured one, the author showed how this overpressure decreases as the Eulerian mesh size decreases. This work present the results of a 3D numerical simulations of damage caused by air blast on fully clamped CFRP rectangular plates.

Blast test description

Blast tests were performed at a stand-off distance of 150 mm in order to apply the load in the centre of the plate and to reduce boundary effects. The targets were 800 mm by 800 mm square with a thickness of 27 mm, clamped using a purpose built test rig and a spherical explosive charge supported as shown in Figure 1. Aluminum honeycomb crush blocks were used to record the deformation of the target. Passive and active crush blocks were used, positioned at the quarter span point of the target, to measure peak and timed panel deflection. The active crush block contained three contact switches allowing the initial dynamic response of the panel to be recorded for comparison with modelling results. The explosive selected was the C-4 (Composition 4), that is a common military plastic explosive.

The trials were performed on different target materials [17]. In this work results relative to standard quasi isotropic laminate composite, carbon fibre (Tenax STS 24k NCF) in standard epoxy matrix (+-45/90,0)_{7s}, loaded by 750g and 825g C-4 are presented and discussed.

Figure 1 – Overview of blast test ring

For all the panels under assessment, delamination most extensive affected area occurred midway through the thickness (Figure 2 a). In order to assess damage through the laminates thickness a reservoir of water was placed on top (rear) surface of the plates and the panel was examined for water leakage. The damage observed in failed tests did not correspond to a hole in the target (Figure 2 b).

Figure 2 – Details of delamination damage at 750g C-4 (a) and rear face condition after blast impact at 825g C-4 (b)

FE model

The FE models were made of three components: frame, bolts and target (Figure 3). The simulation were performed with the commercial FEM code LS-DYNA. Multi-layers shell elements with interface delamination model was generated to simulate the composite target. Only 14 layers were modelled instead of the 56 layers that really make the panel in order to avoid a too high number of elements. Hence one layer was made of four integration points and each of them is associated to a different layer (+45/90,0).

Figure 3 – Composite FEM model

Fixed boundary conditions were applied on the lower surface of frame in order to simulate the rest of the basement and symmetry boundary conditions were applied on the nodes lying on plane XZ and YZ. The contacts between target and bolts and between target and frame were modelled using contact algorithms. Besides, confining nodes of bolts and frame were merged, hence no contact card was applied between these components. The total number of elements for the composite model was about 169.000 with a size mesh of about 2.6 mm. Belytschko-Tsay under-integrated formulation was applied to composite shell elements. Hourglass viscous form control was applied to under-integrated shell elements with an hourglass coefficient of 1e-3. The Chang-Chang composite failure criteria [18] was used for modeling in-plane failure of the unidirectional layers. The test modeled in this work are reported in Table 1.

Table 1- Tests Simulated

Charge weight	600	750	825	863	900
CFRP	✓	✓ ✓	X		x
	✓ Passed test	x failed test	■ FEM simulation performed		

Composite material properties

CFRP UD lamina strength properties were provide by QinetiQ [1]. In Table 2 the material properties used are illustrated.

Table 2 - composite material properties

Density [kgm⁻³]	1600	E₁ [GPa]	127	E₂ [GPa]	17
G₁₂ [GPa]	6	Longitudinal Tensile Strength [MPa]	1500	Longitudinal Compressive Strength [MPa]	1200
Transverse Tensile Strength [MPa]	50	Transverse Compressive Strength [MPa]	250	Shear Strength [MPa]	70

A delamination model was applied between each shell layers interface based on the Dycoss Discrete Crack Model [20]. The model works through the contact tiebreak formulation [19]. Tie-break contact allows the modelling of connections which transmits both compressive and tensile forces with optional failure criteria. Before failure, tie-break contact works both in tension and compression. After failure, this contact behaves as a surface-to-surface contact with thickness offsets. Hence, after failure, no interface tension is possible.

Blast model

To model the blast phenomena a Multi Material Arbitrary Eulerian Lagrangian approach was used (Figure 4). The explosive and air mesh were simulated. The interface between Eulerian ambient (air + explosive) and Lagrangian structure (target) were also defined.

Figure 4 – MMALE model

Table 3 - Air and explosive LS-DYNA cards [mm, kg, ms]

*MAT_NULL (air)								
ro	pc	mu	terod	cerod	Ym	pr		
1.225E-9	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
*EOS_LINEAR_POLYNOMIAL (air)								
C0	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	E0	V0
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.4000	0.4000	0.000	2.5e-4	1.000
*MAT_HIGH_EXPLOSIVE_BURN (C-4)								
ro	d	pcj	beta	k	G	sigy		
1.6e-6	8193.000	28.040001	0	0	0	0		
*EOS_JWL (C-4)								
A	B	R1	R2	Omeg	E0	V0		
609.77002	12.95000	4.5000	1.4000	0.25000	9.000	1.000		

Eulerian ambient was modeled with 1 point MMALE solid element with ambient pressure outflow option in order to allow the fluid flowing outside the mesh boundaries.

Symmetry boundary conditions were guaranteed by the slip condition applied to symmetry plane YZ and XZ (fluid flow's normal component equal to zero). The number of Eulerian elements is about 171.000. To model air and explosive material behaviors *MAT_NULL and *MAT_HIGH_EXPLOSIVE_BURN were used respectively. These cards require an EOS: for the air a linear polynomial EOS was used, while for the explosive the JWL EOS. The values input into the models are illustrated in Table 3 [21]. The contact between the fluid flow and the target was modeled to provide the coupling mechanism for modeling Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI). In the case of composite model an FSI card was defined for each ply giving a total number of 14 FSI cards in order to guarantee the interaction also in the case of through thickness shells composite failure (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – FSI

Results

In general, during blast loading on panels a compressive stress wave within the material is generated by the impact of pressure wave at the front face of the target. This compressive wave propagates throughout the material until it reaches the rear surface of target, where it is reflected as a tensile wave. In a composite material laminate, the initial compressive stresses may produce some degree crushing failure in the composite matrix. The tensile reflected wave starting from the back surface produces delaminations. In the following instants, the pressure on the target distributes on the whole material and generates a bending load on the panel, which can also lead to fibre breakage. In Figure 6 numerical dynamic deflection compared with experimental measure is illustrated. If in the first instants of deflection numerical model appears fairly over-stiff, while the numerical steady-state response tends to the same deflection value and rate of the experimental data. In the following figures results are summarised in terms of damage map. The damage maps represent the composite failure distribution and they are split in fibre/matrix - tension/compression damages. The damage is maximum if it is equal to 0 (blue regions), minimum if it is equal to 1 (red regions). Each element is removed by LS-DYNA when the damage is equal to 0 in all its own integration points. Maximum integration point values (conservative condition) are illustrated in exploded view (z direction - factor 2) to better visualize the damage in each ply. The experimental damage assessment performed after blast tests was not possible to numerically perform through the approach used in this work. In consideration that the damage assessment plays a key role in the comparison process of

numerical and experimental results, a numerical failure criterion different from the experimental one was defined in order to evaluate model prediction capability. The matrix failure, both in tension and in compression, was the numerical damage assessment criterion selected. In fact, the water penetration through the panel thickness of experimental damage assessment can be much more easily associated to matrix failure rather than to fibres breakage.

The compressive matrix damage zone was found along the whole central thickness for CFRP models only in the case of 875 g blast load, while is almost absent in the case of 750 g blast load. This agrees very well with the experimental data showing that the composite panel was not able to resist to the considered blast load as found during the experimental campaign. Finally, in Figures 9 and 10 numerical results are also compared with provided real damage morphology showing a fairly good agreement.

Figure 6 – Dynamic deflection

Figure 7 – Damage maps 750g

Figure 10 – CFRP rear damage

Conclusions

The work investigated the performance of a fully clamped rectangular CFRP target subjected to C-4 blast loads using commercial FEM explicit code LS-DYNA. A Multi Materials Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian (MMALE) formulation was employed to simulate the blast loading phenomenon. Assuming the composite matrix failure as damage criteria, the models very well simulated the overall experimental CFRP armour response. A reasonably good agreement between numerical and experimental results was found in terms of damage morphology.

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